

1 **Islands of runs of homozygosity indicate selection signatures in OAR6 of French**
2 **dairy sheep**

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12 **Running title:** Runs of homozygosity and selective pressure in sheep

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19 **Abstract**

20 Runs of homozygosity (ROH) are contiguous homozygous segments of the genome
21 where the haplotypes inherited from each parent are identical. The occurrence of ROH
22 is not randomly distributed across the genome, and ROH islands across many animals
23 may be the result of selective pressure. The objective of this study is to demonstrate
24 that the presence of ROH islands may be indicative of selection signatures in French
25 dairy sheep breeds and subpopulations. The data set available included animals
26 (artificial insemination males) from various breeds and subpopulations: Basco-
27 Béarnaise breed (BB, 321 individuals); Manech Tête Noire breed (MTN, 329
28 individuals); Manech Tête Rousse breed (MTR, 1906 individuals); Lacaune
29 Confederation subpopulation (LACCon, 3030 individuals); and Lacaune Ovitest
30 subpopulation (LACOvi, 3114 individuals). Animals were genotyped with the
31 Illumina OvineSNP50 BeadChip. After applying filtering criteria, the genomic data
32 included 38287 autosomal SNPs distributed across 26 chromosomes and 8700
33 individuals. One island of ROH was detected on OAR6 in the same genomic position
34 across animals (between 30 – 40 Mb). Global Wright's differentiation coefficients
35 (F_{ST}) for two SNPs within this ROH island were high (0.67 – 0.68). The linkage
36 disequilibrium between both SNPs was also elevated (0.98). The divergence in allele
37 frequencies in those SNPs grouped BB, MTN and MTR breeds in one cluster, and
38 LACCon and LACOvi subpopulations in another cluster. The closest candidate genes
39 are *NCAPG* and *LCORL*, which have been reported to be under positive selection and
40 suggested to control weight and height in sheep. The preliminary identification of
41 ROH can suggest the presence of selection. However, for the identification of
42 potential candidate genes, ROH detection should be combined with other approaches
43 to improve mapping accuracy.

44

45 Sheep, one of the first domesticated species, have a manageable size and the ability to
46 adapt to different climates and diets with poor nutrition (Zeder, 2008). From its
47 domestication, sheep spread world-wide, and a large variety of breeds was shaped by
48 natural and artificial selection, with different morphology, coat color or specialized
49 production in meat, milk or wool. These selection mechanisms have left signatures in
50 domestic animal genomes, such as decreased genetic diversity and long haplotypes
51 (Rochus et al., 2018).

52

53 Different methods varying in the underlying assumptions have been proposed to
54 detect selection signatures, such as F_{ST} (Weir and Cockerham, 1984), extended
55 haplotypes of homozygosity (EHH) (Sabeti et al., 2002) and iHS (integrated haplotype
56 homozygosity score) (Voight et al., 2006). Genome-wide scans for detecting selection
57 signatures have been successfully applied to domestic animals based on these
58 approaches.

59

60 The availability of large numbers of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) has
61 made these markers appropriate to distinguish old (short runs) from new (long runs)
62 identical by descent segments (Howrigan et al., 2011). Accordingly, SNPs can be
63 used for the detection of genomic regions where an increase on homozygosity has
64 occurred. Although the detection of regions of homozygosity can be interfered by the
65 presence of copy number variation or large distance between SNPs (Nandolo et al.,
66 2018), the identification of runs of homozygosity (ROH) is a potential alternative to
67 detect signatures of selection. The occurrence of ROH is heterogeneous along the
68 genome due to the stochastic nature of the recombination events. Consequently, the
69 detection of ROH islands may be indicative of selective pressure. ROH can provide a

70 better understanding about the population selection history, supporting the discovery
71 of genes or genomic regions under selective pressure (Zhang et al., 2015).

72

73 Selection of French dairy sheep has been implemented for each local breed and
74 subpopulation separately. There are three major regions for sheep milk production.
75 The first one is around the Roquefort (Aveyron) area, with the Lacaune breed, whose
76 elite population (breeding flocks) actually consists of two subpopulations: Lacaune
77 Confederation (LACCon) and Lacaune Ovitest (LACOvi), which split around 1975
78 and proceed in parallel selection schemes. In the Western Pyrenees mountains, there
79 are three breeds: Manech Tête Rousse (MTR), Manech Tête Noire (MTN) and Basco-
80 Béarnaise (BB). A third region is Corse island, but Corsican sheep were not included
81 in the present study. All the breeds in this study (LACCon, LACOvi, MTR, MTN,
82 BB) have been selected for production (milk yield and composition) and functional
83 (resistance to mastitis, udder morphology) traits with varying intensities.

84

85 The objective of this study was to demonstrate that the presence of ROH islands may
86 be indicative of selection signatures in French dairy sheep breeds and subpopulations.

87

88 Rams were genotyped with the OvineSNP50 BeadChip (Illumina Inc., San Diego,
89 CA). The number of genotyped animals were 321, 329, 1906, 3030, and 3114 for BB,
90 MTN, MTR, LACCon and LACOvi, respectively. These are artificial insemination
91 rams representing several years of birth (10-15) and overlapping generations, and they
92 illustrate the genetic variability of each breed. SNP quality control included the
93 absence of parent-offspring Mendelian segregation incompatibilities ($< 3\%$), SNP call
94 rate $> 97\%$, and large deviations from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (SNP with $p <$

95 10^{-6} were discarded). The final dataset included 8700 genotyped individuals and
96 38287 autosomal SNPs. Markers were positioned using the sheep (*Ovis aries*) genome
97 assembly 3.1 (OAR 3.1). See Legarra et al. (2014) for more details.

98

99 Plink software version 1.9 (Chang et al., 2015) was used to calculate the genetic
100 differentiation coefficient F_{ST} (Weir and Cockerham, 1984) between subpopulations
101 and breeds with the option --fst. Significance level was evaluated using Lewontin and
102 Krakauer (1973) statistical test (Bonhomme et al., 2010) and applying a Bonferroni
103 correction using the total number of markers.

104

105 The rehh R package (Gautier and Vitalis, 2012) with the default values was used to
106 calculate iHS , where an extreme score (> 2 or < -2) provides a strong signal of
107 selection (Voight et al., 2006), indicating the most extreme 5% of iHS values.

108

109 The software detectRUNS (Biscarini et al., 2018) was used to detect ROH with a
110 sliding-window based method and the following criteria: a minimum length of 250
111 Kb, a minimum of 20 homozygous SNPs, the maximum distance allowed between 2
112 consecutive homozygous SNPs in a run was 1 Mb, the minimum density was 1 SNP
113 per 10 Kb, and no missing or heterozygous genotypes were allowed.

114

115 The correlation between the number of times a SNP is included within a ROH and F_{ST}
116 (or iHS) was calculated for all SNPs in each chromosome.

117

118 The average genetic differentiation coefficient across breeds and subpopulations was
119 0.0576 ± 0.0003 . The genome-wide distribution of global differentiation coefficient

120 for each SNP revealed the highest selection signal was detected on OAR6 (Figure
121 1.a). The two highest ranked SNPs (*OAR6_41583796.1*; $F_{ST} = 0.675$; $P = 4.03 \times 10^{-9}$
122 and *OAR6_41709987.1*; $F_{ST} = 0.670$; $P = 4.01 \times 10^{-9}$) were located at 37423374 bp
123 and 37542319 bp, respectively. Other three significant SNPs were also detected on
124 OAR6 nearby the two highest ranked SNPs (36205101bp, 36972847 bp and
125 37318895 bp). In addition, six isolated significant SNPs were detected on OAR3 (2
126 SNPs; 61548300 bp and 61577699 bp), OAR11 (1 SNPs; 40118817 bp), OAR13 (2
127 SNPs; 46841439 bp and 62932554 bp) and OAR16 (1 SNPs; 33219172 bp). The F_{ST}
128 values for the remaining autosomes were not as higher as the F_{ST} values observed for
129 the two highest ranked SNPs on OAR6. Results obtained for *iHS* derived statistic are
130 shown in Figure 1.b. A total of 1735 significant SNPs were detected in all
131 chromosomes for *iHS* statistic. Agreement between significant SNPs for F_{ST} and *iHS*
132 was detected only for one SNP on OAR13 on 46841439 bp. Ninety five significant
133 SNPs for *iHS* were observed in OAR6. At least two significant SNPs for *iHS* on
134 OAR6 (*OAR6_39124095.1* and *OAR6_42392875.1*) were close (35063421 bp and
135 38193916 bp, respectively) to the highest significant SNPs for F_{ST} .
136
137 The highest correlation between F_{ST} and the number of times that a SNP is in a ROH
138 was observed in OAR6 for LACovi and LACCon subpopulations and MTR breed
139 ranging between 0.36 and 0.42 (Figure 1.c). However, the highest correlation (0.31)
140 between *iHS* and the number of times that a SNP is in a ROH was observed in OAR26
141 for MTR breed (Figure 1.d). The correlation between *iHS* and the number of times
142 that a SNP is in a ROH does not support the OAR6 signal observed in Figure 1.c. This
143 can be related to the fact that F_{ST} and *iHS* have identified different significant SNPs
144 within OAR6.

145

146 - Figure 1 -

147

148 The F_{ST} values for SNPs *OAR6_41583796.1* and *OAR6_41709987.1* between pairs of
149 breeds and / or subpopulations are shown in Table 1. The highest F_{ST} values were
150 observed between Western Pyrenees breeds and Lacaune subpopulations.

151

152 - Table 1 -

153

154 The allele frequencies observed for both SNPs also diverged for the same allele
155 between Western Pyrenees breeds (BB, MTN and MTR) and Lacaune subpopulations
156 (LACCon and LACovi). For SNP *OAR6_41583796.1* the allele frequency ranged
157 between 0.62 – 0.95 in Western Pyrenees breeds, and between 0.07 – 0.13 in Lacaune
158 subpopulations for the same allele. In other words, they were nearly fixed for opposite
159 alleles. Similar results were observed for SNP *OAR6_41709987.1*. In addition, both
160 SNPs were in nearly complete linkage disequilibrium (calculated from allele
161 frequencies $r^2 = 0.98$).

162

163 Figure 2.a shows the ROH island detected for each animal on OAR6. The frequency
164 of ROH was high between 30 – 40 Mb in LACovi and LACCon subpopulations, and
165 MTR breed. This ROH island included both SNPs *OAR6_41583796.1* and
166 *OAR6_41709987.1* (the highest ranked SNPs for F_{ST}). The ROH island detected on
167 OAR6 involves a large interval, compared to the reduced interval obtained from the
168 two most significant SNPs in the F_{ST} analysis. This suggests that F_{ST} approach is more
169 precise than ROH methodology in terms of mapping accuracy. However, the gene

170 mapping accuracy of ROH is affected by the criteria used to define a ROH, which in
171 turns depend on the available genotype SNP density. In any case, ROH signals
172 suggest that the hitchhiking effect involves a large region of homozygosity around the
173 potential candidate genes. Some agreements between ROH islands and selection
174 signatures have been previously reported in the literature (*e. g.* Purfield et al., 2017).
175 Other regions of high percentage of times each SNP falls inside a ROH were also
176 detected in OAR2, OAR4 and OAR10 (Figure 2.b), but no concordance between
177 those homozygous regions and strong differentiation coefficient was observed. This
178 lack of agreement could be attributed to demography and recombination events giving
179 rise to ROH (Bosse et al., 2012).

180

181 - Figure 2 -

182

183 The selection signal identified on OAR6 has been previously reported in the literature
184 (*e. g.* Al-Mamun et al., 2015; Manunza et al., 2016; Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2017).
185 Fariello et al. (2014) found on OAR6 between 33.22-41.02 Mb a signal of selection,
186 and the candidate genes associated to this position were *ABCG2* (located in OAR6
187 between 36514210 bp and 36556824 bp on OAR 3.1 reference genome), *NCAPG*
188 (located in OAR6 between 37256548 bp and 37333851 bp on OAR 3.1 reference
189 genome) and *LCORL* (located in OAR6 between 37365236 bp and 37452332 bp on
190 OAR 3.1 reference genome). *ABCG2* has been associated to a strong QTL for milk
191 production in cattle, and *NCAPG* and *LCORL* have been associated to fetal growth
192 (Eberlein et al., 2009) and calving ease in cattle (Druet et al., 2013). Plassais et al.
193 (2019) detected a significant association with *LCORL* and height, weight and life-span
194 in canids. Accordingly, *NCAPG* and *LCORL* genes have agricultural and adaptive

195 importance, and have been associated with allelic heterogeneity in selection signatures
196 (Rochus et al., 2018).

197

198 Naval-Sanchez et al. (2018) analyzed 43 sheep breeds and 17 Asiatic mouflon with
199 genome sequence resolution. On OAR6, between 37.42-37.51 Mb, they found a
200 signature of selection and the associated gene to this position was *LCORL*, which has
201 a function related with weight and height (as the *NCAPG* gene). These authors
202 indicated that domestic sheep contain a selective sweep in the *LCORL* promoter
203 region, while mouflon contain a sweep downstream of *NCAPG*.

204

205 To conclude, ROH and single marker F_{ST} analyses agreed that selection signatures
206 exists around markers *OAR6_41583796.1* and *OAR6_41709987.1* that were located
207 near *NCAPG* and *LCORL* genes. One of the factors involved in shaping ROH patterns
208 in French Dairy sheep was selection. Accordingly, the preliminary identification of
209 ROH can suggest the presence of selection. However, for the identification of
210 potential candidate genes, ROH detection should be combined with other approaches
211 to improve mapping accuracy.

212

213 **References**

214

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314

315 **Funding**

316

317 This study was supported by the European Unions' Horizon 2020 Research &
318 Innovation programme under grant agreement N° 772787 – SMARTER, ARDI (grant

319 agreement EFA 208/16) from POCTEFA funds, and GDivSelGen action (INRA
320 SelGen metaprogram).

321

322 **Acknowledgements**

323

324 We thank two anonymous referees for useful suggestions on the manuscript.

325 GenoToul bioinformatics platform Toulouse Midi-Pyrenees provided computing and
326 storage resources.

327

328 **Conflict of interest**

329

330 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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339 **Table 1.** Differentiation coefficient between pairs of breeds and / or subpopulations
340 for SNP *OAR6_41583796.1* (above the diagonal) and *OAR6_41709987.1* (below the
341 diagonal).

342

	BB	MTN	MTR	LACCon	LACovi
BB		0.077	0.131	0.652	0.777
MTN	0.076		0.403	0.481	0.639
MTR	0.129	0.397		0.784	0.860
LACCon	0.649	0.479	0.782		0.019
LACovi	0.771	0.633	0.856	0.018	

343

344 BB: Basco-Béarnaise, MTN: Manech Tête Noire, MTR: Manech Tête Rousse,
345 LACCon: Lacaune Confederation, LACovi: Lacaune Ovitest.

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Legends to Figures

350

351 **Figure 1.** (a) Genome-wide differentiation coefficient (F_{ST}) across chromosomes.
352 Orange dashed line indicates the significance level after Bonferroni correction. (b)
353 Integrated haplotype homozygosity score (iHS). Black dashed lines indicate the iHS
354 threshold (> 2 or < -2). (c) Correlation between F_{ST} and the number of times that a
355 SNP is in a ROH. (d) Correlation between iHS and the number of times that a SNP is
356 in a ROH. LACOvi (Lacaune Ovitest), LACCon (Lacaune Confederation), MTR
357 (Manech Tête Rouse), MTN (Manech Tête Noire) and BB (Basco-Béarnaise).

358

359 **Figure 2.** (a) Runs of homozygosity detected for each animal on OAR6. Mbps:
360 Megabases. (b) Percentage of times each SNP falls inside a ROH. LACOvi (Lacaune
361 Ovitest), LACCon (Lacaune Confederation), MTR (Manech Tête Rouse), MTN
362 (Manech Tête Noire) and BB (Basco-Béarnaise).

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366 **Figure 1**

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376 **Figure 2**

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